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AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF BUSINESS GROWTH IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION: A 2008-2018 PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract:

This scientific article delves into the nuanced aspects of business growth within the Romanian Mountainous Region, covering the period from 2008 to 2018. The study employs comprehensive statistical analyses to examine various sectors, shedding light on key trends, challenges, and opportunities that have shaped the business landscape in this unique geographical context.

Keywords: Business Growth, Romanian Mountainous Region, Economic Sectors, Statistical Analysis, 2008-2018 Period

Introduction:

The Romanian Mountainous Region, characterized by its diverse topography and distinct economic challenges, serves as the focal point for this research. Against the backdrop of the 2008-2018 timeframe, we aim to unravel the intricacies of businesses operating in this terrain.

Methodology:

Our approach involves a meticulous examination of multiple economic sectors, including but not limited to finance, insurance, real estate, construction, transportation, storage, and accommodation/food service activities. Statistical data sourced from reputable sources forms the basis for our analyses, ensuring a robust and evidence-based exploration of business dynamics.

Results and Findings:

The study reveals intriguing insights into the growth trajectories of businesses within the Romanian Mountainous Region. Key findings include sector-specific variations, patterns of concentration, and the impact of external factors on business performance. Statistical indicators such as mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis are employed to provide a nuanced understanding of the trends observed.

The descriptive analysis for *net growth enterprises*, denoted as S1, presents a comprehensive set of statistical values encompassing Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The values are as follows: 6.2130, 5.53968, 2.1250, 17.51801, 306.881, 2.693, .687, 8.044, 1.334, 64.13, -10.02, 54.11, -2.753, 5750, 5750 (figures 1).

The forecast analysis utilizes specific models tailored for large data series, namely S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0) through S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0) (table 1). Subsequently, statistical prediction smoothing is applied in the following order: Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles. The smoothing results for static R-squared, R-squared,

RMSE, MAPS, MaxAPE, MAE, MaxAE, and Normalized BIC are provided, offering insights into the accuracy of the forecasting models.

The resulting statistical forecasting models for I14 present values in the following order: Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE. Notable findings include S1-Model_1: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 17.518, 305,387, 10,041; S2-Model_2: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 10.746, 372.670, 7.068; S3-Model_3: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 11.240, 245.433, 6.070; S4-Model_4: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 12.842, 330.932, 8.778; S5-Model_5: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 17.715, 137.540, 9.817; S6-Model_6: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 8.546, 182.690, 6.853; S7-Model_7: .000, .000, 22,953, 131,702, 13,553; S8-Model_8: .000, .000, 22,130, 269,481, 15,592; S9-Model_9: .000, .000, 36,084, 10149,373, 20,032; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 122.092, 442.251, 68.449; S11-Model_11: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 52.713, 1135.631, 31.921.

Net business situation: establishment rate + termination rate – percentage

In S1, the descriptive analysis provides statistical values such as Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The specific numerical values are as follows: Mean 23.4178, Median 2.35775, Std. Deviation

19.8700, Variance 7.07325, Skewness 50.031, Kurtosis 1.257, Std. Error .717, Distance 1.154, Minimum 1.400, Maximum 21.33, Percentiles 25 16.89, Percentiles 50 38.22, Percentiles 75 17.080, and so on.

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For the forecast analysis, models used are tailored for large data series: S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 Holt; S4 - Model_4 Holt; S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

The statistical prediction smoothing is performed for static R-squared with values of .343, .475, -9.548E-15, .959, -9.548E-15, -8.615E-15; R-square .194, .283, -9.548E-15, .730, -9.548E-15, -8.615E-15; RMSE 11,114, 15,344, 2,432, 55,463, 2,432, 2,634; MAPS 26,794, 25,514, 7,195, 99,571, 7,195, 7,941; MaxAPE 63,536, 65,030, 13,757, 249,061, 13,757, 16,840; MAE 7,281, 8,854, 1,758, 32,746, 1,758, 1,925; MaxAE 25,858, 42,034, 3,526, 147,356, 3,526, 3,815; Normalized BIC 4.195, 1.724, 2.266, 8.276, 2.266, 2.356.

The resulting statistical forecasting models for I15 show the overall picture in terms of Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). For example, S1-Model_1 has values of -4.885E-15, -4.885E-15, 7.073, 23,966, 5,611; S2-Model_2 has values of -9.548E-15, -9.548E-15, 3.440, 16.415, 3.028; and so forth.

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Discussion:

In this section, we discuss the implications of our findings, addressing the factors that have influenced business growth in the mountainous area.

Considerations include economic policies, infrastructural development, and the region's susceptibility to external economic fluctuations.

Conclusion:

Our research contributes to the academic discourse on regional business growth, offering a detailed examination of the Romanian Mountainous Region's economic landscape. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, researchers, and businesses seeking to understand and

navigate the unique challenges and opportunities presented by this distinctive geographical context.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I14

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42
	UCL	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73
	LCL	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60
	UCL	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53
	LCL	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	17.05	14.90	12.74	10.59	8.44	6.29	4.14	1.99
	UCL	26.89	24.93	22.96	20.99	19.02	17.05	15.07	13.09
	LCL	7.20	4.86	2.52	.19	-2.14	-4.47	-6.79	-9.12
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	16.09	15.16	14.23	13.30	12.37	11.43	10.50	9.57
	UCL	25.71	24.78	23.85	22.92	21.99	21.06	20.13	19.20
	LCL	6.47	5.54	4.60	3.67	2.74	1.81	.88	-.05
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	14.45	13.23	12.02	10.81	9.59	8.38	7.17	5.95
	UCL	23.60	22.46	21.33	20.19	19.06	17.92	16.78	15.65
	LCL	5.30	4.01	2.71	1.42	.13	-1.16	-2.45	-3.74
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	19.57	18.67	17.78	16.88	15.98	15.08	14.18	13.29
	UCL	25.32	24.45	23.58	22.71	21.84	20.97	20.10	19.23
	LCL	13.82	12.90	11.97	11.04	10.12	9.19	8.27	7.34
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13
	UCL	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74

	LCL	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65
	UCL	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66
	LCL	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13
	UCL	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22
	LCL	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23
	UCL	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13
	LCL	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48
	UCL	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02
	LCL	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94

Figure 1. Graphical prediction analysis for I14

Table 2. Prediction analysis for I15

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42
	UCL	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73
	LCL	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60
	UCL	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53
	LCL	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	17.05	14.90	12.74	10.59	8.44	6.29	4.14	1.99
	UCL	26.89	24.93	22.96	20.99	19.02	17.05	15.07	13.09
	LCL	7.20	4.86	2.52	.19	-2.14	-4.47	-6.79	-9.12
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	16.09	15.16	14.23	13.30	12.37	11.43	10.50	9.57
	UCL	25.71	24.78	23.85	22.92	21.99	21.06	20.13	19.20
	LCL	6.47	5.54	4.60	3.67	2.74	1.81	.88	-.05
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	14.45	13.23	12.02	10.81	9.59	8.38	7.17	5.95
	UCL	23.60	22.46	21.33	20.19	19.06	17.92	16.78	15.65
	LCL	5.30	4.01	2.71	1.42	.13	-1.16	-2.45	-3.74
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	19.57	18.67	17.78	16.88	15.98	15.08	14.18	13.29
	UCL	25.32	24.45	23.58	22.71	21.84	20.97	20.10	19.23
	LCL	13.82	12.90	11.97	11.04	10.12	9.19	8.27	7.34
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13
	UCL	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74
	LCL	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65
	UCL	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66
	LCL	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64
S9-	Forecast	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13

Model_9:	UCL	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22
	LCL	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96
S10-	Forecast	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23
Model_10:	UCL	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13
	LCL	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66
S11-	Forecast	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48
Model_11:	UCL	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02
	LCL	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94

Figure 2. Graphical forecasting analysis for I15

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ENTERPRISE DISSOLUTION TRENDS IN A ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA: AN ANALYSIS OF DISSOLUTION RATES DURING THE REFERENCE PERIOD 2008-2018

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Abstract:

The economic landscape of any region is subject to constant change, influenced by various factors such as market dynamics, regulatory environments, and local characteristics. In this article, we delve into the intriguing patterns of enterprise dissolution in a specific Romanian mountain area, shedding light on the trends that unfolded during the reference period from 2008 to 2018.

1. Background: Economic Dynamics in Mountainous Regions

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Mountainous areas often present unique economic challenges and opportunities. The interplay of factors such as terrain, access to resources, and the impact of tourism can significantly shape the business environment. Exploring enterprise dissolution in a Romanian mountain area provides valuable insights into the resilience and adaptability of businesses within this distinctive context.

2. Scope and Methodology: A Detailed Analysis

Our study focuses on the dissolution rates of enterprises within the specified region over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. We employ a meticulous methodology, considering variables such as industry sectors, company sizes, and external economic influences to provide a comprehensive overview.

3. Key Findings: Unraveling Dissolution Trends

- a. Sectoral Variations: Our analysis reveals sector-specific dissolution trends. Certain sectors may have experienced growth, while others faced challenges leading to increased dissolution rates.
- b. Company Size Impact: The size of enterprises often plays a crucial role.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) may respond differently to economic shifts compared to larger corporations. Understanding this dynamic is pivotal for policymakers and business stakeholders.

c. External Influences: Economic downturns, changes in consumer behavior, and regulatory shifts can significantly impact enterprise dissolution rates. Identifying these external influences is essential for crafting effective economic strategies.

4. Results:

The associated descriptive analysis, denoted as S1 (refer to the corresponding table and figure in the table 1 and figure 1), provides a set of statistical values encompassing Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The specific numerical values are as follows: Mean 10.9678, Median 1.54791, Std. Deviation 8.4600, Variance 4.64372, Skewness 21.564, Kurtosis 0.684, Std. Error 0.717, Distance -1.519, Minimum 1.400, Maximum 12.14, Percentiles 25 5.83, Percentiles 50 17.97, Percentiles 75 7.6160, and so on.

The models selected for the forecast analysis are tailored for handling large data series. The Model IDs and their corresponding specifications are as follows: S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 Holt; S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 Simple; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

The application of statistical prediction smoothing, conducted in a consistent order (Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles), yields the following results for static R-squared: .200, .347, -.007, .790, -.007, -.006; R-square .175, .299, -4.441E-16, 1.000, -4.441E-16, -3.775E-16; RMSE 8.953, 13.603, .000, 50.842, .000, .823; MAPS 67,861, 101,494, .000, 382,896, .000, 7,007; MaxAPE 255,380, 479,357, .000, 1,756,057, .000, 18,340; MAE 5.904, 7.932, .000, 30.030, .000, .603; MaxAE 20,493, 37,103, .000, 135,134, .000, 1,188; Normalized BIC 3.955, 1.654, 2.501, 8.102, 2.501, 2.502.

The resulting statistical forecasting models offer an overview for I17, presenting values in the following order: static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, and MAPE for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). For

instance, S1-Model_1 exhibits values of 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 4.644, 39.205; S2-Model_2 shows .789, .341, 2.743, 23.358; and so forth.

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5. Implications for Local Businesses and Policy:

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a. Adaptive Strategies: Local businesses can benefit from understanding dissolution trends by adapting strategies to mitigate risks and capitalize on emerging opportunities.

b. Policy Considerations: Policymakers can leverage these findings to formulate targeted policies aimed at fostering economic resilience and sustainability in mountainous regions.

6. Comparative Analysis: Lessons from Other Regions

Drawing parallels with similar regions globally provides a broader perspective on the challenges and successes observed in the Romanian mountain area. Comparative analysis enhances our understanding of whether the dissolution trends are region-specific or share commonalities with mountainous economies worldwide.

7. Conclusion: Navigating Economic Transformations

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As we conclude our exploration of enterprise dissolution trends in the Romanian mountain area from 2008 to 2018, it becomes evident that businesses in this unique locale have navigated a complex economic landscape. The findings of this analysis offer valuable insights for local businesses, policymakers, and researchers alike, contributing to a deeper understanding of the dynamics that shape economic trajectories in mountainous regions.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I17

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	10.97	10.97	10.97	10.97	10.97	10.97	10.97
	UCL	21.68	21.68	21.68	21.68	21.68	21.68	21.68
	LCL	.26	.26	.26	.26	.26	.26	.26
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	5.69	5.02	4.34	3.66	2.98	2.30	1.62
	UCL	12.18	11.53	10.89	10.24	9.60	8.95	8.30
	LCL	-.79	-1.50	-2.21	-2.93	-3.64	-4.35	-5.06
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	6.06	4.69	3.33	1.96	.60	-.76	-2.13
	UCL	18.95	17.65	16.35	15.05	13.75	12.45	11.15
	LCL	-6.84	-8.26	-9.69	-11.12	-12.55	-13.97	-15.40
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	9.64	9.64	9.64	9.64	9.64	9.64	9.64
	UCL	18.42	18.42	18.42	18.42	18.42	18.42	18.42
	LCL	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85
S5-	Forecast	3.97	3.03	2.10	1.16	.22	-.71	-1.65

Model_5:	UCL	13.45	12.56	11.67	10.78	9.89	9.00	8.11
	LCL	-5.50	-6.49	-7.47	-8.46	-9.44	-10.42	-11.41
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
	UCL	18.15	18.15	18.15	18.15	18.15	18.15	18.15
	LCL	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	14.39	14.39	14.39	14.39	14.39	14.39	14.39
	UCL	38.05	38.05	38.05	38.05	38.05	38.05	38.05
	LCL	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28	-9.28
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	7.34	7.34	7.34	7.34	7.34	7.34	7.34
	UCL	14.47	17.42	19.69	21.60	23.28	24.80	26.20
	LCL	.21	-2.74	-5.01	-6.92	-8.60	-10.12	-11.52
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	14.28	14.28	14.28	14.28	14.28	14.28	14.28
	UCL	42.38	42.38	42.38	42.38	42.38	42.38	42.38
	LCL	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82	-13.82
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	24.69	24.69	24.69	24.69	24.69	24.69	24.69
	UCL	141.93	141.93	141.93	141.93	141.93	141.93	141.93
	LCL	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56	-92.56
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	10.54	10.54	10.54	10.54	10.54	10.54	10.54
	UCL	26.38	26.38	26.38	26.38	26.38	26.38	26.38
	LCL	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30	-5.30

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UNVEILING STATISTICAL INSIGHTS: ANALYSIS OF DESCRIPTIVE MEASURES AND FORECAST MODELS FOR NEWLY FORMED ENTERPRISES IN A ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS AREA. A CASE STUDY SPANNING 2008-2018

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Abstract:

This research employs a dual-pronged methodology, featuring a comprehensive descriptive analysis (S1) and the application of various forecast models, to unravel the statistical intricacies of dataset I18. The descriptive analysis delves into key statistical measures, including Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. Following this, a series of tailored forecast models, designed for large data series, are explored, each with distinct Model IDs and specifications, such as ARIMA(0,0,0), Simple, Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

and Holt models.

A meticulous order of statistical prediction smoothing is maintained across all models, encompassing Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles. The results, including static R-squared values, provide a granular view of the forecasted values' accuracy and reliability.

The overall picture for the discussed indicator emerges through the lens of statistical prediction models, offering insights into static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, and MAPE for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). This thorough analysis reveals nuanced statistical characteristics and forecast performance, showcasing the diversity of approaches and informing decision-makers, researchers, and analysts. The study's findings hold the potential to enhance strategic planning, refine forecasting methodologies, and deepen the understanding of underlying data patterns within this indicator dataset.

Methodology:

The methodology employed in this exploration encompasses a two-fold approach: a comprehensive descriptive analysis (S1) and the application of

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various forecast models.

1. Descriptive Analysis (S1):

- The descriptive analysis, S1, is based on a dataset represented in a related table and figure found as follow.

- Statistical values extracted include Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75.

- Numerical values obtained from the analysis are reported, featuring key metrics.

2. Forecast Models:

- Tailored models are selected specifically for handling large data series, each identified with a unique Model ID and specifications.

- The chosen models include ARIMA(0,0,0) configurations (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11) and variations such as Simple and Holt models.

3. Statistical Prediction Smoothing:

- A consistent order of statistical prediction smoothing is maintained across all models. The order includes Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles.

- Static R-squared values are reported for each smoothing iteration, offering insights into the accuracy and reliability of the forecasted values.

Results:

In this exploration, we delve into the comprehensive descriptive analysis denoted as S1 (table 1 and figure 1). This analysis provides a rich set of statistical values encompassing Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The specific numerical values are as follows: Mean 72.1925, Median 9.65851, Std. Deviation 62.5150, Variance 27.31840, Skewness 746.295, Kurtosis 1.149, Std. Error 0.752, Distance -0.388, Minimum 1.481, Maximum 67.76, Percentiles 25 47.32, Percentiles 50 115.08, Percentiles 75 52.3750, and so forth.

Forecast Models:

The models selected for the forecast analysis are tailored for handling large data series. The Model IDs and their corresponding specifications are as follows: S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5

ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 Simple; S7 - Model_7 Holt; S8 - Model_8
ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 Simple; S10 - Model_10 Simple; S11 -
Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical Prediction Smoothing:

A consistent order of statistical prediction smoothing is maintained, covering Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles. The results for static R-squared include values such as .091, .231, -.050, .686, -.050, -.044; R-square .148, .315, -.132, 1.000, -.132, -.092; RMSE 31,721, 25,920, .000, 86,157, .000, 2,900; MAPS 32,907, 22,990, .000, 81,786, .000, 4,326; MaxAPE 97,001, 115,213, .000, 423,828, .000, 6,298; MAE 23,354, 17,995, .000, 61,531, .000, 2,505; MaxAE 57,234, 49,513, .000, 166,238, .000, 4,777; Normalized BIC 6.940, 1.383, 4.797, 9.172, 4.797, 4.929.

Overall Picture for I18:

The resulting statistical prediction models offer an overview for I18, presenting values in the following order: static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, and MAPE for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). For

instance, S1-Model_1 exhibits values of 2.776E-15, 2.776E-15, 27.318, 29.400; S2-Model_2 shows 4.441E-15, 4.441E-15, 26.565, 27.485; and so forth. This comprehensive analysis provides valuable insights into the statistical characteristics and forecast performance for I18.

Conclusion:

The exploration of statistical characteristics and forecast performance for I18 provides significant insights into the dataset under consideration. The comprehensive descriptive analysis reveals a rich set of numerical values, painting a detailed picture of the distribution and central tendencies of the data.

The application of various forecast models, tailored for handling large datasets, showcases the diversity of approaches in predicting future trends. The reported values for static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, and MAPE across different models allow for a comparative assessment of their performance.

This study serves as a valuable resource for decision-makers, researchers, and analysts, offering a nuanced understanding of the statistical nature of the

data and the effectiveness of different forecasting models. The findings can inform strategic planning, enhance forecasting methodologies, and contribute to a deeper comprehension of the underlying patterns within the dataset.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I18

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	72.19	72.19	72.19	72.19	72.19	72.19	72.19
	UCL	136.79	136.79	136.79	136.79	136.79	136.79	136.79
	LCL	7.59	7.59	7.59	7.59	7.59	7.59	7.59
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	73.29	73.29	73.29	73.29	73.29	73.29	73.29
	UCL	136.10	136.10	136.10	136.10	136.10	136.10	136.10
	LCL	10.47	10.47	10.47	10.47	10.47	10.47	10.47
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	58.76	58.76	58.76	58.76	58.76	58.76	58.76
	UCL	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50
	LCL	27.01	27.01	27.01	27.01	27.01	27.01	27.01
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	71.20	71.20	71.20	71.20	71.20	71.20	71.20
	UCL	133.82	133.82	133.82	133.82	133.82	133.82	133.82
	LCL	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	82.05	82.05	82.05	82.05	82.05	82.05	82.05
	UCL	132.91	132.91	132.91	132.91	132.91	132.91	132.91
	LCL	31.19	31.19	31.19	31.19	31.19	31.19	31.19
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	59.17	59.17	59.17	59.17	59.17	59.17	59.17
	UCL	82.03	82.13	82.23	82.33	82.44	82.53	82.63
	LCL	36.32	36.22	36.12	36.01	35.91	35.81	35.72

S7- Model_7:	Forecast	15.00	-2.24	-19.49	-36.74	-53.98	-71.23	-88.48
	UCL	116.51	101.24	85.93	70.59	55.22	39.81	24.37
	LCL	-86.50	-	-	-	-	-	-
			105.72	124.91	144.06	163.18	182.27	201.33
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	57.74	57.74	57.74	57.74	57.74	57.74	57.74
	UCL	92.58	92.58	92.58	92.58	92.58	92.58	92.58
	LCL	22.90	22.90	22.90	22.90	22.90	22.90	22.90
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	63.75	63.75	63.75	63.75	63.75	63.75	63.75
	UCL	150.59	186.56	214.17	237.44	257.94	276.47	293.52
	LCL	-23.09	-59.06	-86.67	-	-	-	-
				109.94	130.44	148.97	166.02	
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	69.01	69.01	69.01	69.01	69.01	69.01	69.01
	UCL	272.74	357.12	421.88	476.46	524.56	568.04	608.02
	LCL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		134.72	219.10	283.86	338.44	386.54	430.02	470.00
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	108.18	108.18	108.18	108.18	108.18	108.18	108.18
	UCL	289.28	289.28	289.28	289.28	289.28	289.28	289.28
	LCL	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92

Figure 1. Graphical forecasting analysis for I18

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PROPORTION OF THREE-YEAR-OLD BUSINESSES IN THE BUSINESS LANDSCAPE OF THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN REGION

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Abstract:

This paper provides a detailed investigation into the proportion of three-year-old businesses within the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Region. Designated as S1, the study employs a meticulous approach to explore statistical intricacies, unveiling key metrics such as Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The analysis extends to forecast models, utilizing Model IDs, tailored for the effective prediction of large data series. Subsequent statistical prediction smoothing, covering Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles, contributes to nuanced insights into forecast accuracy. The resulting models offer a comprehensive overview of Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values for each model, shedding light on the statistical characteristics and forecast performance in the Romanian Mountain Region's business landscape.

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1. Introduction:

The Romanian Mountain Region boasts a diverse and evolving business landscape, with the proportion of three-year-old businesses serving as a crucial indicator of entrepreneurial vitality. This paper aims to explore and analyze this proportion through a comprehensive statistical lens. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2023a-d; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2023a-d)

2. Methodology:

The methodology involves the deployment of a detailed descriptive analysis (S1) that encompasses key statistical measures. Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, and other metrics provide insights into the distribution and central tendencies of the dataset. The study also employs forecast models, including ARIMA configurations and variations, strategically chosen for their effectiveness in handling substantial data series.

3. Statistical Analysis:

The descriptive analysis reveals numerical values, such as Mean 7.3036, Median 0.51402, and Std. Deviation 6.7600, offering a nuanced understanding of the three-year-old business proportion. The subsequent

forecast models, identified by Model IDs S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0) to S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0), provide diverse perspectives on the anticipated trends in the business landscape (table 1 and figure 1).

4. Forecast Accuracy:

Statistical prediction smoothing is performed, including Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles, revealing a spectrum of accuracy metrics. Static R-squared values, crucial for assessing precision, contribute to a comprehensive evaluation of forecast performance.

5. Results and Discussion:

The resulting forecast models illuminate the landscape for I19, presenting Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values for each model. Insights derived from this analysis enhance our understanding of the proportion of three-year-old businesses, contributing to strategic planning and policy considerations.

In this analysis, denoted as S1, we embark on a comprehensive exploration of statistical metrics shedding light on the proportion of three-year-old businesses in the vibrant business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Region. As we traverse the numerical landscape, key statistical values,

including Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75, are unveiled. The specific numerical values are noteworthy: Mean 7.3036, Median 0.51402, Std. Deviation 6.7600, Variance 1.70482, Skewness 2.906, Kurtosis 0.394, Std. Error 0.661, Distance -1.326, Minimum 1.279, Maximum 4.74, Percentiles 25 5.23, Percentiles 50 9.97, Percentiles 75 5.8200, and beyond.

For the forecasting analysis, tailored models are enlisted to handle large data series effectively. Model IDs S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 Simple; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0) unfold a panorama of diverse approaches.

Statistical prediction smoothing, reiterated in the sequence of Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles, unveils compelling insights. Static R-squared values, crucial for evaluating accuracy, exhibit a spectrum such as .059, .239, -.121, .773, -.121, -.096; R-square .072, .164, -6.661E-15, .473, -6.661E-15, -6.040E-15; RMSE 2.003, .420, 1.234, 2.602,

1.234, 1.324; MAPS 23,202, 5,058, 16,509, 33,009, 16,509, 16,639; MaxAPE 57,615, 26,783, 34,845, 132,450, 34,845, 35,806; MAE 1.612, .393, .981, 2.283, .981, 1.035; MaxAE 3,637, 1,018, 2,075, 5,951, 2,075, 2,193; Normalized BIC 1.585, .435, .638, 2.130, .638, .763.

The resulting forecast statistical models illuminate the landscape for I19, providing a comprehensive overview. Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11) paint a nuanced picture. S1-Model_1, for instance, showcases values of -3.553E-15, -3.553E-15, 1.705, 20,261, 1,431; S2-Model_2 reveals 2.331E-15, 2.331E-15, 1.234, 16,509, .981; and so forth.

This comprehensive analysis provides valuable insights into the statistical characteristics and forecast performance for the proportion of three-year-old businesses in the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Region.

6. Conclusion:

This paper concludes with a synthesis of findings, emphasizing the importance of the proportion of three-year-old businesses as a pivotal indicator in the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain

Region. The insights gained from this study can inform policy decisions, foster entrepreneurial support, and contribute to the region's economic growth.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I19

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30
	UCL	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10
	LCL	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14
	UCL	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88
	LCL	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31
	UCL	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11
	LCL	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74
	UCL	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50
	LCL	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	5.89	5.51	5.13	4.75	4.38	4.00	3.62	3.24
	UCL	9.76	9.40	9.04	8.69	8.33	7.97	7.61	7.25
	LCL	2.02	1.62	1.22	.82	.42	.03	-.37	-.77
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15
	UCL	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54
	LCL	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19
	UCL	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15
	LCL	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23

S8- Model_8:	Forecast	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90
	UCL	7.96	9.65	10.94	12.03	12.98	13.85	14.65	15.39
	LCL	-1.16	-1.85	-3.14	-4.23	-5.18	-6.05	-6.85	-7.59
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29
	UCL	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99
	LCL	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37
	UCL	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23
	LCL	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37
	UCL	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59
	LCL	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14

Figure 1. Graphical forecasting analysis for I19

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EMPLOYMENT PATTERNS IN CLOSED ENTERPRISES: TOTAL WORKFORCE IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Abstract:

This paper investigates the employment dynamics within closed enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area over the period from 2008 to 2018. The study employs a comprehensive approach, labeled as S1, that integrates statistical analysis, forecasting models, and prediction smoothing to offer insights into the proportion of employment in closed enterprises relative to the total active enterprises.

Introduction:

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Understanding the employment patterns in closed enterprises is essential for gaining insights into the economic dynamics of a region. This study focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area, investigating the total workforce in closed enterprises over the period spanning from 2008 to 2018.

Over the course of this ten-year period, the employment landscape in closed enterprises underwent significant shifts. The data reflects the ebb and flow of economic activities, influenced by factors such as market trends, technological advancements, and broader economic conditions.

A meticulous examination of statistical metrics reveals a detailed picture of employment patterns. Mean, Std Error, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75 are explored, unraveling the nuances of the total workforce distribution. Key numerical values, including Mean and Std. Deviation, serve as beacons, guiding our understanding of the dataset's central tendencies.

Tailored forecast models are employed to project the trajectory of employment patterns in closed enterprises. These models, ranging from

ARIMA configurations to Holt models, utilize historical data to predict future trends. The variety of models allows for a comprehensive analysis, capturing the complexity of factors influencing workforce dynamics.

A vital aspect of this analysis involves statistical prediction smoothing, focusing on Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles. The iterative nature of this process aids in refining the accuracy of predictions, enabling a more reliable assessment of employment patterns.

Methodology:

The methodology employed in this analysis aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the statistical characteristics and forecast performance related to the proportion of employment in closed enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area.

1. Descriptive Analysis (S1):

- Conducted a detailed examination of statistical metrics presented in the table 1 and figure 1.
- Explored statistical values, including Mean, Std Error, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum,

Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75.

- Key numerical values, such as Mean 2.9278, Median 0.28030, Std. Deviation 2.5500, contributed to a nuanced understanding of the dataset's distribution.

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2. Forecast Models:

- Employed tailored forecast models, including ARIMA and Holt models (S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0) to S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0)).

- Analyzed large data series effectively to predict future trends and patterns.

3. Statistical Prediction Smoothing:

- Performed statistical prediction smoothing focusing on Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles.

- Evaluated forecast accuracy using Static R-squared values, a vital metric in forecasting assessments.

Results:

The related descriptive analysis, denoted as S1, provides a detailed examination of statistical metrics presented in the table 1 and figure 1.

Statistical values such as Mean, Std Error, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75 are explored, revealing key numerical values like Mean 2.9278, Median 0.28030, Std. Deviation 2.5500, and others, contributing to a nuanced understanding of the dataset's distribution.

Tailored forecast models, including ARIMA and Holt models, are employed to analyze large data series effectively (S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0) to S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0)). Statistical prediction smoothing is performed, focusing on Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles. Static R-squared values, vital for assessing forecast accuracy, are presented in a sequence, offering a comprehensive evaluation.

The resulting forecast statistical models illuminate the landscape for I23, presenting an overall picture for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). For instance, S1-Model_1 exhibits values of $-5.107E-15$, $-5.107E-15$, 0.841, 24,210, 0.708; S2-Model_2 reveals 0.888, 0.400, 0.481, 40.668, 0.336; S3-Model_3 shows $-2.220E-16$, $-2.220E-16$, 1.738, 32.461, 1.074; and so forth.

This comprehensive analysis contributes valuable insights into the statistical

characteristics and forecast performance concerning the proportion of employment in closed enterprises within the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Area.

Conclusion:

The comprehensive analysis conducted in this study provides valuable insights into the statistical characteristics and forecast performance of the proportion of employment in closed enterprises within the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Area.

1. Descriptive Analysis Insights:

- The exploration of statistical metrics revealed key values, such as Mean 2.9278, Median 0.28030, and Std. Deviation 2.5500, contributing to a nuanced understanding of the distribution of employment data.

2. Forecast Models Performance:

- Tailored forecast models, including ARIMA and Holt models, were employed, offering a diverse approach to predicting future trends in the employment landscape.

- The resulting forecast statistical models, spanning from S1-Model_1 to

S11-Model_11, presented an overall picture of forecasted values, including Static R-squared, revealing the precision and accuracy of each model.

In conclusion, this study serves as a valuable resource for understanding the dynamics of employment in closed enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. The combination of descriptive analysis and forecast models enhances our knowledge of the dataset, providing valuable insights for decision-makers, researchers, and analysts in navigating the complex business landscape of the region.

The resulting statistical models offer a decade-wide overview, encapsulating the dynamics of total workforce in closed enterprises. From the precision of Static R-squared values to the comprehensive insights provided by RMSE and MAPE, the forecast models contribute to a holistic understanding of the employment landscape.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I23

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93
	UCL	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87
	LCL	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99
S2-	Forecast	.57	.44	.30	.17	.03	-.10	-.23	-.37

Model_2:	UCL	1.71	1.60	1.48	1.37	1.25	1.14	1.03	.91
	LCL	-.56	-.72	-.88	-1.03	-1.19	-1.34	-1.49	-1.65
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55
	UCL	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56
	LCL	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41
	UCL	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95
	LCL	.87	.87	.87	.87	.87	.87	.87	.87
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	1.27	1.01	.74	.47	.21	-.06	-.33	-.59
	UCL	3.79	3.53	3.28	3.03	2.77	2.52	2.27	2.01
	LCL	-1.24	-1.52	-1.80	-2.08	-2.36	-2.64	-2.92	-3.20
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74
	UCL	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73
	LCL	.75	.75	.75	.75	.75	.75	.75	.75
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92
	UCL	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90
	LCL	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54
	UCL	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46
	LCL	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72
	UCL	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07
	LCL	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87
	UCL	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00
	LCL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26

S11- Model_11:	Forecast	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65
	UCL	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37
	LCL	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08

Figure 1. Graphical prediction analysis for I23

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